

Chemical Examination of *Butea Frondosa* Flower Isolation of a Crystalline Glucoside of Butin.

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Butea Frondosa, called *Dhak* or *Palas* in Hindusthani is a fine tree belonging to the natural order of *Leguminosæ* and is very common in India. The flowers, which in the dried state are known as *tisu* or *palas-ke-phul*, have either a bright yellow colour with bright orange spots or have an orange colour with red spots. They are the source of one of the few surviving members of a large number of natural organic colouring matters and are still used in India especially in the United Provinces. Large quantities of the flowers are collected in March and April and employed by the people to produce a yellow dye much used during the "Holi Festival." "The flowers are supposed to be astringent, depurative, diuretic and aphrodisiac; as a poultice they are much used to disperse swelling and promote diuresis and the menstrual flow. They are given to enciente women in the case of diarrhœa, and are applied externally in orchitis" Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", 1918, Part I, p. 443).

A preliminary examination of these flowers was made by Hummel and Caralls (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 10, 11) who isolated a substance termed "butein" $C_{15}H_{14}O_5$, and supposed this to be the true colouring matter. This product in some respects yielded shades which were not unlike those of fisetin obtained from young fustic. Hill (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 19, 133) extracted from these flowers a colouring matter in the form of lemon-yellow crystals which gave the reactions of fisetin. He noted further the presence of a phlobaphene which on fusion with caustic potash gave phloroglucinol and protocatechuic acid. Finally Hummel and Perkin (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 134; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1463) examined the flowers and isolated by acid hydrolysis of the aqueous extract a colourless crystalline compound, butin $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ melting at 224-26° and traces of an orange-red crystalline substance, butein $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ melting at 213-15° in 0.04% yield. They also proved the non-occurrence of fisetin in the flowers and were of opinion that they

contain but a trace of free butin or butein. As a result of the dyeing tests with mordanted calico, they assumed that butin and butein were present in the form of glucosides which they failed to isolate.

The constitutions which Perkin and Hummel (*loc. cit.*) assigned to butin and butein are those of 7:3':4'-trihydroxyflavanone (I) and 2:4:3':4'-tetrahydroxychalkone (II) respectively and they established the correctness of these formulæ by the synthesis of butin and butein trimethyl ether.

(I)

(II)

Somewhat later Göschker and Tambor (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3502) prepared butein itself by treating protocatechuic aldehyde and resacetophenone in boiling alcohol with potassium hydroxide and found it to be identical in all respects with the natural product. Later on attempts of Shinoda, Sato and Kawagoe (*J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1929, 49, 123) to repeat their synthesis were unsuccessful. They, however, succeeded in synthesising butein by the condensation of the acid chloride of dicarbethoxycafeic acid with resorcinol.

In view of the uncertainty as to the probable existence of a glucoside in the flowers the present authors undertook a critical investigation and have isolated a colourless crystalline glucoside, $C_{27}H_{32}O_{15} \cdot 2H_2O$ melting sharply at 193.5° and giving on hydrolysis two molecules of glucose and one of butin. A satisfactory process for the isolation of the diglucoside of butin, the first recognised member of the flavanone group, has been worked out. The glucoside has

been termed butrin in view of the fact that it is a glucoside of butin. The yield of butrin is on the whole 2.6% and that of the phlobaphene and of butein isolated are 1% and 0.003% respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dried flowers were obtained from the local market and their petals were collected and ground to a coarse powder. The powdered flower-petals were extracted in 50 g. lots in a Soxhlet's apparatus with various organic solvents. The solvent was subsequently evaporated and the extract thus obtained dried to a constant weight at 100°. The results are given below.

Alcoholic extract.—Orange-yellow, soft crystalline mass with a peculiar odour. It gives an olive-green colour with ferric chloride, a brownish-yellow granular precipitate with lead acetate and reduces Fehling's solution. Microscopic examination of the substance revealed the presence of an yellow crystalline colouring matter, a colourless crystalline substance, a wax and chlorophyll, yield 21.46%.

Acetone extract.—Similar to the alcoholic extract, but much lighter in colour. A lemon-yellow crystalline substance could be easily discerned through the matrix of sticky matter, yield 13.56%.

Ethyl acetate extract.—Light yellow semi-solid substance containing crystalline matter in suspension, yield 5.5%. It had properties similar to the above.

Benzene extract.—Light yellow substance with properties similar to the above, yield 0.01%.

The dried flowers when completely incinerated left 11.52% of flesh coloured ash containing 2.98% of water-soluble and 8.54% of water-insoluble inorganic constituents. The water-soluble portion was mainly potassium carbonate with traces of sodium phosphate and chloride. The water-insoluble portion contained calcium, magnesium aluminum and traces of zinc together with sulphate, phosphate and carbonate.

Isolation of butrin.—For complete examination, 4 kg. of the coarsely powdered flowers were in lots of 700 g. repeatedly extracted with rectified spirit in a 5 litre extraction flask until the extract was no longer coloured. The combined orange-yellow extracts were distilled until most of the solvent had been recovered and the residue boiled with frothing. It was then allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature for about a week by which time a large amount of soft crystalline matter had separated out. The thick crystalline magma

was slightly thinned by the addition of about one tenth of its volume of alcohol and filtered at the pump with good suction. The residue was washed with alcohol, until it had assumed a lemon-yellow colour. After drying at first in the air and then in the steam-oven it was obtained as an yellow crystalline gritty mass melting at $135-39^{\circ}$ and it was of a glucosidal nature. It was repeatedly extracted with hot benzene in order to remove chlorophyll and waxy matter. Then it dissolved fairly readily in cold water and this rather unusual property suggested that it was probably a salt of the dyestuff and on examination it proved to be the case since it contained potassium in organic combination in considerable quantity. By repeated crystallisations from alcohol it could only be obtained as a soft yellow crystalline mass containing, in between, clusters of white tiny needles. The substance on repeated extraction with boiling acetone gave a very small amount of an intensely sweet substance which was not further examined. The melting point of the substance rose to 190° after three crystallisations from hot water when it was obtained in the form of tiny colourless needles and after two crystallisations from alcohol the melting point rose to 193.5° and did not rise any further. This substance on slow and careful crystallisation is obtained in the form of glistening needles often as long as 1 cm. The dried substance has the composition $C_{27}H_{32}O_{15} \cdot 2H_2O$ and loses the two molecules of water of crystallisation when heated at 120° for 15 hours. The anhydrous substance is extremely hygroscopic and readily absorbs two molecules of water of crystallisation when exposed to air. It has all the properties of a glucoside since it reduces Fehling's solution only after hydrolysis with mineral acids. Further crops of the lemon-yellow gritty mass were obtained by concentrating the successive mother-liquors and the aqueous washings but they required, after removal of waxy matter and chlorophyll, several crystallisations from hot water before they were sufficiently pure to be crystallised finally from alcohol.

It is slightly soluble in cold water to a perfectly colourless solution which remains undecomposed on boiling. It is insoluble in acetone, ether, benzene, bromoform, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform and petroleum ether; slightly soluble in cold and moderately soluble in hot ethyl and methyl alcohols and glacial acetic acid and is very readily soluble in pyridine to a colourless solution. In caustic alkalis and alkali carbonates, however, it dissolves to a deep yellow solution and on boiling it undergoes decomposition giving a deep orange solution. It gives no precipitate in alcoholic solution with silver

nitrate and calcium chloride, but gives a pale yellow precipitate with lead acetate. It does not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride; with excess of methyl or ethyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid and magnesium powder it gives an intense violet colouration which turns brown on dilution with water, thereby showing that the substance is a flavanone derivative (Tsujimura, *Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res. Tokyo*, Vol. VI, 12, III; Kuroda, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 137, 753). It gives an intense red colouration with concentrated hydrochloric acid which disappears on dilution. With concentrated sulphuric acid it first turns orange-red and finally dissolves to an orange-red solution which turns deep red on warming. It does not contain any OMe or OEt groups. [Found: loss of H_2O at 120° , 5.84, 5.79; $C_{27}H_{32}O_{15}$, $2H_2O$ requires H_2O , 5.69%. The air-dried substance gave on combustion C, 51.24, 51.26, 51.21; H, 5.69, 5.84, 5.78; and the fully dried substance gave C, 54.32, 54.19; H, 5.67, 5.64. $C_{27}H_{32}O_{15}$, $2H_2O$ requires C, 51.26; H, 5.69%; and $C_{27}H_{32}O_{15}$ requires C, 54.3; H, 5.6 per cent].

Isolation of butein.—A portion of the filtrate after the separation of the butrin was treated with excess of hot alcoholic lead acetate and the resulting bright orange-yellow precipitate filtered off and washed first with alcohol and then with hot water. This on decomposition with hydrogen sulphide in alcoholic suspension and after filtering off the lead sulphide gave a deep orange solution which on concentration deposited no crystalline mass. It was treated with hot water when a viscous deep red mass separated and the latter on repeated extraction with water left behind a phlobaphene melting at 115° which was also isolated by Hill (*loc. cit.*).

The aqueous solutions after concentration at first under ordinary pressure and then under reduced pressure slowly deposited a small amount of an orange precipitate, which on repeated crystallisations from dilute alcohol was obtained in the form of bright yellow needles melting at $213-15^\circ$. It gave an olive-brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, a deep red precipitate with alcoholic lead acetate and dissolved in alkalis and alkali carbonates to a deep orange-red solution. It was identified to be butein which Perkin (*loc. cit.*) isolated in traces from the flowers of *Butea Frondosa*. [Found (dried at 160°): C, 66.07; H, 4.57. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.17; H, 4.41 per cent].

The alcoholic filtrate and washing from the lead acetate precipitate gave a bright yellow precipitate on treatment with excess

of basic lead acetate. This on working up in accordance with the method described above gave an orange-yellow solution which on concentration deposited a considerable quantity of an yellow crystalline mass which on purification was found to be butrin. No other glucoside or substance of interest could be isolated from these mother-liquors.

Hydrolysis of Butrin and Formation of Butin.

Butrin (2 g.) was hydrolysed by heating with dilute sulphuric acid (5%, 100 c.c.) under reflux on the water-bath for 2 hours. The substance gradually dissolved forming a light yellow solution, which on standing for several days deposited a quantity (0.8 g.) of pale yellow needles. These on several recrystallisations from alcohol were obtained as a practically colourless substance crystallising in needles and melting at 224-25° identified as the butrin of Perkin. [Found (in the substance dried at 140°): C, 66.07; H, 4.41. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.27; H, 4.4 per cent].

The mother liquor, left after the hydrolysis of butrin, reduced Fehling's solution strongly and on treatment with phenylhydrazine gave an osazone which melted at 202° and was identical with phenyl-glucosazone. The sugar contained in butrin, therefore, must be glucose, and the former must be the di-glucoside of butin.

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Further work on this subject is in progress.